

ATTENTION TO CHILDREN'S EDUCATION — FOUNDATION FOR THE FUTURE

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***Abstract.** This article is devoted to the importance of science and education in the lives of young people, who are the owners of the future.*

***Keywords:** science, education, education, state policy for youth, the right to education in general, development of the education system.*

What kind of person he will grow up to be in the future, what profession he will choose, and whether he will be able to realize his dreams largely depend on the child's knowledge. Therefore, great importance is attached to the fundamental reform of the education and training system in our country, the acquisition of modern knowledge and the more thorough acquisition of required professions by our children, and the improvement of the quality of personnel training based on advanced international standards. Work in this regard is being carried out consistently and meets the requirements of the times.

Improving the effectiveness of reforms in the field of education is one of the urgent tasks of today. All possibilities are involved for this. Great forces and means have been mobilized for comprehensive development of the education system and training of qualified personnel. Such attention has served to change the quality of teaching and education in schools, and to improve the teaching staff.

In today's rapidly changing and developing world, only the young generation with modern knowledge and skills can find its rightful place. More than 60 percent of the population of Uzbekistan are young people. Today, training them on the basis of high standards, forming the ability to think in a new, innovative way is one of the urgent tasks.

The task of training modern, creative and unique personnel with unique thinking is also urgent. Because the purpose of science is not to memorize, but to understand and reason. If a person has intelligence, he thinks and observes, analyzes any issue, sees with his own eyes, knows deeply what is good and what is bad. It is necessary to create a methodology that encourages students not only to remember, but also to think, which is of primary importance in the educational process.

Uzbekistan is a country of young people. Therefore, special attention is paid to the education and development of young people. First of all, the legal basis for organizing work in this field is constantly being improved. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Basics of State Policy Regarding Youth" covers issues of legal and social protection of young people, support of their talents. and the law regulates the powers of authorities and management bodies in this regard, as well as other social relations in the field.

It is also noteworthy that the right of young people to receive free general education is guaranteed. Today, in order to support talented young people in our country, the modern education provided to young people in Presidential schools, Temurbek school, creative and specialized schools is a solid foundation of the New Renaissance.

The gratifying thing is that in the conditions of the times and socio-economic changes, the demands and needs of today's youth are being studied, and the door of new privileges and opportunities is being opened.

The initiatives of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev in improving the youth policy in the new Uzbekistan based on the needs of the times should be highlighted. The constant attention of the head of our state to the development of youth is clearly visible, especially in the educational reforms. The success of these reforms is increasing the confidence of young people in the state and laws.

In addition, it should be noted that the largest investment in our country is focused on supporting education, and this is one of the highest goals of our nation. Certain directions of the head of state's appeals are directed to the field of education.

The development of the education system in our country has risen to the level of state policy. The task of reforming this most important sector, where the future of the state is concentrated, is being solved step by step. Development of human capital is one of the seven priorities of the strategy for the development of New Uzbekistan in 2022-2026. The 43rd and 44th goals of the strategy, among other tasks, are to improve the quality of education in schools, to raise the knowledge and skills of pedagogical personnel to the international level.

The level of education has a significant impact on various aspects of a person's life, adherence to a healthy lifestyle, the level of perception of culture and art, and the right attitude to political processes. It is not for nothing that the right to education is defined as one of the basic human rights in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. As explained in the report of the World Bank "The level of well-being of skills", the wealth of countries is determined by human capital, the level of education and skills of the population.

In fact, our increasing attention to education, our ability to provide the young generation with quality education is a foundation stone for Berunis, Ibn Sinas, Alisher Navoi, and Ulugbeks to grow up again from our country, which has a great history and world-recognized scientists serves as.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized that improving the quality of education is the only right way to develop the new Uzbekistan, and it is worth remembering that he quoted our grandfather Yusuf Khos Hajib: "Wherever there is ingenuity there will be greatness, where there is knowledge there will be greatness." It was a clear example that if we want to create a great future, we will not be able to achieve our goals without increasing attention to education and providing quality education.

In Uzbekistan, the funds spent on the education of the young generation with high intellectual potential are considered not as expenses, but as an investment in the future. Today, we are all witnesses to the fact that a number of decisions and decrees, laws, and the State National Program for the Development of School Education approved in 2004, and the large-scale work being carried out in this regard, have fundamentally changed our country. The system of education and upbringing, but also the life of our society as a whole, gave an "explosive effect" in a huge, positive sense.

World experience shows that innovation processes are effectively carried out, technologies and products are commercialized only in countries with a comprehensively developed economic system. In this process, it is important to support the state participation, the real sector of the economy and the innovative activities of leading companies. After all, science and education form

the basis of this integration mechanism, which ensures the technical development of the state and the socio-economic development of the society.

In this sense, the fairs and projects of innovative ideas, technologies and projects, which are traditionally held at the initiative of the President, are aimed at introducing practical research, using their results to strengthen the integration between producers and consumers of innovative products. is becoming one of the important mechanisms.

In recent years, especially in the field of education, great positive indicators have been achieved, which rightly arouses a sense of joy and pride in every citizen of Uzbekistan. Today, representatives of the new generation who think in a new way, who imagine their future only with the further prosperity of their beloved Motherland, are taking a bold step. Boys and girls know several foreign languages, know how to manage modern equipment and technologies, and their eyes burn with passion to serve their people.

When you see such young people, you envy them in a good way. At the same time, you involuntarily remember the recent past. After all, for almost a century, we did not have the opportunity to talk about our glorious history, the great contribution of our ancestors to the world civilization. During the time of the former regime, they looked at us with fear and took all measures to avoid accidentally meeting foreign scientists. And the first President of the Republic of Azerbaijan started a valiant struggle for the restoration of our national values from the first days of independence, the results of which are now clearly visible.

In fact, the history and spiritual wealth of the nation was so confused that clarifying and establishing the truth required a long and arduous struggle and tireless defense of one's positions. If we look at the scope of the work carried out in this regard today, it can be understood that due to the consistent measures taken by our Honorable President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, we have completely freed ourselves from the consequences of the period between the years of independence and the ancient culture of the last century.

Therefore, whoever you talk to today, you will definitely be satisfied with the peace and contentment of your life, peace of mind for the future of your children. First of all, we are a nation that cares about children. This is the essence of the state policy implemented under the leadership of the President. In a country where the education of the young generation is considered as the future of the nation, the children will grow up to be perfect people who are no less than anyone and nothing.

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